

EUROPE

The 'science of science'
***Why measuring research is necessary to
improve the way it is funded***

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RAND Europe

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RAND Europe

- **Independent not-for-profit public policy research institute**
 - *“help improve policy and decision making through research and analysis”*
- **Part of the global RAND Corporation**
- **Work across the breadth and depth of government**
- **Strongly held values of quality and objectivity**
- **Provider of evidence**

RAND Europe research agenda

Policy-focused programmes

Outline

- **The why and how of research evaluation**
- **Two case studies**
 - **Estimating the economic returns from research**
 - **Mapping the impact of research**
- **Lessons and discussion**

Why evaluate research?

- **Advocacy**
 - 'make the case' for research funding
- **Accountability**
 - To taxpayer, donors etc
- **Analysis**
 - What works in research funding?
- **Allocation**
 - What to fund (institution, field, people ...)

How do you evaluate research

- **Benchmarking**
- **Surveys**
- **Logic models**
- **Bibliometrics**
- **Case studies**
- **Economic**
- **Peer review**

Focus of today's talk is on two studies

	Advocacy	Accountability	Analysis	Allocation
Benchmarking		✓		
Surveys		✓		
Logic Models			✓	
Bibliometrics				✓
Case studies			✓	✓
Economic	✓			
Peer review				✓

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Case studies			✓	✓
Economic	✓			
Peer review				✓

Key messages

- **Know why you are measuring research**
 - **What is the objective of the research evaluation?**
- **Use a ‘multi-method, multi-dimensional’ approach**
 - **Don’t rely on one method (e.g., bibliometrics)**
- **(Research) evaluation is not easy**
 - **No (research) funder has the answer**
- **Need to move from advocacy to accountability**
 - **Need ‘science of science’ to understand what works**
 - **Need a practical evidence base for science policy**
 - **Need to ‘walk the talk’**

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Estimating the economic returns from research: An example of evidence driven advocacy

Background on history

- **US “Exceptional returns” study (Murphy & Topel, 2003)**
 - The return is *20 times greater* than average annual spending on medical research
- **Australian study (Access Economics, 2003)**
 - For every dollar invested, you get \$5 back—a *return of 500%*
- **UK Academy of Medical Science, 2006**
 - *Medical Research: assessing the benefits to society*
 - “that research funders should support research to assess the economic impact of medical research”.

To calculate the return on investment, we made four key estimates

From 1975-1992, £2 billion in public and charitable funding went to UK cardiovascular research

Cardiovascular research spend (£m, 2005 prices)

From 1985-2005, net cardiovascular health gains totaled about £53 Billion

Total number of QALYs gained due to various interventions, 1985-2005

We examined *research-based* interventions that have contributed to health gains

Quality Adjusted Life Year (QALY)
=
An additional year of quality life

From 1985-2005, net cardiovascular health gains totaled about £53 Billion

Total number of QALYs gained due to various interventions, 1985-2005

- A total of 2.8m QALYs were gained during this 20-year period
- We assigned each QALY a value of £25,000
- We multiplied the two to get £69 billion worth of health gains
- From that total, we subtracted £16 billion in costs to provide the care

This led us to a net total of £53 billion in health gains

The time lag between spending on research and health gain is about 17 Years

Mean age of cited papers is 12.5 years

+

Period between spending and publication

+

Period between recommendation and use

Age and Number of UK Papers Cited in Seven UK Cardiovascular Guidelines (2003-2007)

Time Lag = ~17 years

Combined with the impact of spillover effects, the internal rate of return from public R&D is 39%

Table 6.5: Estimates of social rate of return to public R&D in the agricultural sector

Study	Social rate of return
Griliches (1958)	20–40%
Griliches (1964)	35–40%
Huffman & Evenson (1993)	43–67%
Knutson & Tweeten (1979)	28–47%
Peterson (1967)	21–25%
Schmitz & Seckler (1970)	37–46%

Sources: Griliches (1991), Saller et al. (2000)

$$9\% + 30\% = 39\%$$

Combined, our numbers result in a total return dramatically lower than the other studies

<i>UK consortium study</i>	<i>US study</i>	<i>Australia I study</i>
39%	“20 times”	“500%”

The studies differ in fundamental ways

The US and Australia I studies	The UK Consortium study
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Take a top-down approach<ul style="list-style-type: none">– Look at <i>overall gains</i> in mortality & morbidity—not linked to interventions– Attribute half of these to R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Uses a bottom-up approach<ul style="list-style-type: none">– Identifies <i>research-based interventions</i>– Then quantifies health impact

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<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use a high ‘willingness-to-pay’ value of a life year—3 times that used in our study for a QALY	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Uses a lower ‘willingness-to-pay’ value (as used by Her Majesty’s Government)

Impact

- Used to ‘make case’ for research
- Cited in parliamentary debates
- “Used as evidence as part of the preparation for the spending review and will be in the foreseeable future”
- “few studies that have made a genuine attempt to objectively assess the economic returns of research”

NEWS FEATURE

PHOTO: iStock.com/200

What science is really worth

Spending on science is one of the best ways to generate jobs and economic growth, say research advocates. But as Collin Macilwain reports, the evidence behind such claims is patchy.

President Barack Obama says it. Francis Collins, director of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH), says it. University and research leaders elsewhere are saying it, too. The number one current rationale for extra research investment is that it will generate badly needed economic growth.

“Science is more essential for our prosperity, our health, our environment and our quality of life than it has ever been before,” said Obama, addressing the National Academy of Sciences in Washington DC last year. Getting down to the details, Collins has recently cited a report by Frontier USA, a Washington DC-based health-advocacy group, which found that every US\$1 spent by the NIH typically generates \$2.21 in additional economic output within 12 months.

“Biomedical research has generally been looked at for its health benefits, but the opportunity of science spending are being overlooked. The Frontier USA study used a model developed by the Bureau of Economic Analysis at the US Department of Commerce to deduce the likely benefits of NIH spending in each state. Collins says he has been advised that the approach is “standard and considered reliable”, but some economists question the basic assumptions behind such models — that a certain amount of research input will generate corresponding economic outputs — or that those outputs can be quantified.

Costs or benefits
The problem, economists say, is that the numbers attached to widely quoted economic benefits of research have been extrapolated from a small number of studies.

Research leaders acknowledge that they need better tools. Co-Elim says that the NIH held a workshop with economists in May to see whether it should invest some of its funds into economic outcomes. “We’re very interested in tightening up the evidence base,” he says.

Some of that evidence is already being collected. Under the programme STAR METRICS (Science and Technology in America’s Reinvestment — Measuring the Effects of Research on Innovation, Competitiveness and Science), implemented after the US stimulus package was introduced, the Obama administration is seeking to trace the effect of federal research grants and contracts on outcomes such as employment, publications and economic activity (see *Nature* 24001). The programme’s supporters provide justification for the £ — exactly what research agencies receive under pressure to show outcomes have produced. Grants have always been used for science spending, but it is tough in the United States, stymied by the publication of Galbraith’s thesis, an influential

in published papers — the Nature journals are at present considering urgently necessary ones.

Unknown quantities

It is in researchers’ interests to help funding agencies quantify the economic benefits of their work.

When research agencies are pressed by politicians to quantify the economic value of scientific research, it is only natural that they reach for whatever numbers they can find and then repeat them as well-established fact. Natural, but wrong. The reality is that few of those numbers — typically, assertions that each unit of research investment will yield a certain amount of additional research plays a substantial role in fostering innovation — by which they mean new technologies, services and business methods. They also have good evidence that innovation is essential for strong economic growth, especially when society faces constraints on key inputs such as labour, capital and materials.

Beyond that, they can’t predict which disciplines of scientific research will lead to future innovation — that would require a time machine. Nor, thus far, can they trace how additional research investment will influence a society’s ability to innovate.

The problem is that innovation is not a simple, linear system in which basic research begets technology, and technology begets innovation — although that has always been the easiest model for

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Mapping the impact of research: Developing a dataset of research impacts in the UK

Arthritis Research UK

- Fourth largest charitable funder of research in the UK
- Largest charitable funder of research on arthritis in Europe
- Funds more than £25m of research per annum
- Money raised from donations and legacies

A different type of challenge

End of grant reports

- **Completed at end of grants**
 - Many outputs have not happened
- **Burdensome on researchers**
 - Taking between half a day and a day to complete
- **Relatively unstructured narrative**
 - Hard to aggregate and analyze

Portfolio assessment

- **Should be applicable to all areas of ARC research**
- **Should be applied to every grant**
- **Should minimize the burden on researchers and administration resource**
- **Should collect only what can be analysed**
- **Should provide an overview of ARC portfolio to...**
 - Inform strategy
 - Influence future decisions about funding
 - Form foundation for detailed evaluation

What we did

- Worked with more than 40 ARC researchers to test various approaches
- Developed a web based multi-part questionnaire based on Yes/No questions
- 187 simple, concrete questions:
 - *Through your research did you develop new collaborations with academics? Specifically, did you have initial discussions about collaboration or informal knowledge exchange?*

4.2: Future Research - Further Research

Has your research on this grant led to discussions about possible collaborations, consultancy or similar? If so, which of the following have taken place? Note that we ask about Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs) in this section, as a marker of collaboration; patents and intellectual property impacts are dealt with later in the questionnaire.

1. Interactions with researchers in academia/non-profit organizations:

	Yes	No	Not Known
Have you had initial discussions about collaboration or informal knowledge exchange?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Did these discussions lead to co-applications for funding?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If so, were these successful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, did these discussions lead to co-publications?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, did these discussions lead to Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, did these discussions lead to sharing of reagents without MTAs?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2. Interactions with researchers in industry:

	Yes	No	Not Known
Have you had initial discussions about collaboration or informal knowledge exchange?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If so, did these lead to consultancy?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, collaborations leading to co-publication?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
And/or, an industry initiated research programme?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. Other interactions not captured above

Categorising research impacts

- **Knowledge production**
- **Research targeting and capacity building**
- **Informing policy and product development**
- **Health and health sector benefit**
- **Broader economic benefit**

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Categorising research impacts

- **Research targeting and capacity building**
 - **Further funding**
 - **Interactions with academia**
 - **Interactions with industry**
 - **Research training**
 - **Research careers**
 - **Research tools**

Categorising research impacts

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 - Research careers
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Categorising research impacts

- **Research targeting and capacity building**
 - **Interactions with academia**
 - Have you had **initial** discussions about collaboration of informal knowledge exchange?
 - Did these discussions lead to **co-applications** for funding?
 - Were these **successful**?
 - And/or, did these discussions lead to **co-publications**?
 - And/or, did the discussions lead to **Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs)**?
 - And/or, did these discussions lead to **sharing of reagents** without MTAs?

Categorising research impacts

- **Research targeting and capacity building**

- **Interactions with academia**

- Have you had **initial** discussions about collaboration of informal knowledge exchange? **Yes**
 - Did these discussions lead to **co-applications** for funding? **No**
 - Were these **successful**? **No**
 - And/or, did these discussions lead to **co-publications**? **Yes**
 - And/or, did the discussions lead to **Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs)**? **No**
 - And/or, did these discussions lead to **sharing of reagents** without MTAs? **Yes**

Building the impact array

- Research targeting and capacity building

- Interactions with academia

- Have you had **initial** discussions about collaboration of informal knowledge exchange?
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 - And/or, did these discussions lead to **sharing of reagents** without MTAs?

Yes

No

No

Yes

No

Yes

Building the impact array

Improved on-line survey tool now being used by the English National Institute of Health Research

RAND EUROPE **NHS National Institute for Health Research**

Grant title

SURVEY PROGRESS: 0%

Introduction

Welcome to this sample RAISS questionnaire. As we outlined in the invitation email, the questionnaire is designed to capture research impacts and can be used as a replacement for end of grant reports. It aims to capture the impacts that have arisen from your research grant in a form that is easier to complete and that can be more easily analysed.

Our testing suggests that the questionnaire should take under an hour to fill in. Your answers will be automatically saved each time you move to the next page, so you can complete the questionnaire in more than one sitting.

How to interpret the questions

Since funding organisations have wide-ranging portfolios (from basic biomedical research through to health services research), there is a huge range of potential outputs and impacts. This means that many will not be applicable to your research, or any particular individual's research. However, as it is difficult to know which impacts may arise from which research, we need to allow you to review all the possible impacts, although you are likely to tick only a few.

By their very nature some impacts are difficult to describe exactly, so we would encourage you to skim through the questionnaire to allow you to identify the most appropriate places to indicate the impacts of your grant.

Most of the impact questions ask whether a particular type of impact has arisen and have the following options:

- **Yes** this impact has arisen, and your grant made a substantial contribution to the impact
- **No** this impact has not arisen, although it might arise in the future; or it has arisen but your grant did not make a significant contribution to the impact
- **Not known** you are unaware whether this impact occurred

The focus of this questionnaire is on impacts where this grant made a substantial contribution, ie immediate outcomes of the grant and impacts of subsequent work that developed from the grant. Hence some impacts

<http://demo.raiss.org>

Allows descriptive analysis of different impacts

And the assessment of how this impact occur in time

LagTime Vs % Research Grants by Health Policy Impacts(n=220)

Impacts

- Rolled out by ARUK
- Piloted by CIHR-IMHA
 - International transferable
- Informed UK MRC e-val system
- Being implemented by NIHR
 - Currently surveying 3000 grant holders
- Resulting in unique database whereby the statistical relationship between inputs, outputs and outcomes can be assessed

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A quick resume of analysis and allocation

Analysis

- Identify factors associated with research success
- Case study based
- Build up body of case studies using standard framework
- Identify high and low impact case studies
- Identified factors associated with high and low impact
- Turn into policy recommendations for R&D management

Allocation

- Impact being introduced as part of UK Research Excellence Framework (REF)
- From 2014 c£200m a year allocated to UK universities based on actual impacts
- Impact assessed through peer review of submitted case studies
- First time that impact has been used in allocation on this scale

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Research evaluation requires multiple tools ...

- **Benchmarking**
- **Surveys**
- **Logic models**
- **Bibliometrics**
- **Case studies**
- **Economic**
- **Peer review**

... 'weaving' multiple evidence together in a coherent tapestry

*Upon this gifted age,
in its dark hour,
Rains from the sky a
meteoric shower
Of facts...they lie
unquestioned,
uncombined.
Wisdom enough to
leech us of our ill
Is daily spun; but there
exists no loom
To weave it into fabric*

Edna St Vincent Millay
from 'Upon this age that
never speaks its mind'

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Publications cited in this briefing

- **Advocacy**

- Buxton et al (2008). *Medical Research: What's It Worth?: Estimating the Economic Benefits from Medical Research in the UK*. Wellcome Trust/AMS/MRC.
- http://www.rand.org/pubs/external_publications/EP20080010.html

- **Accountability**

- Wooding et al (2009). *Mapping the Impact: Exploring the Payback of Arthritis Research*. RAND Europe, Cambridge (MG-862-ARC)
- <http://www.rand.org/pubs/monographs/MG862.html>

- **Analysis**

- Wooding et al (2011). *Project Retrosight: Understanding the returns from cardiovascular and stroke research. The Policy Report*. RAND Europe, Cambridge (MG-1079-RS).
- <http://www.rand.org/pubs/monographs/MG1079.html.html>

- **Allocation**

- Grant et al (2010). *Capturing Research Impacts: A Review of International Practice*. RAND Europe, Cambridge (DB-578-HEFCE)
- http://www.rand.org/pubs/documented_briefings/DB578.html

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